

Containers 2: Status of containerisation of Earth Science Models

Milestone MS5

Native build cosmo-2e, 1 member, 4h forecast

Container cosmo-2e, 1 member, 4h forecast

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Overview:

The ESiWACE2 project has put a large effort into utilising containers for production Earth Science models without major impact on performance. During the ESiWACE2 container hackathon¹ (Dec. 3-5, 2019, extensively documented in deliverable D2.8²), six different Earth System models were prepared in containers. In Milestone M2.4³ (MS4) ETH/CSCS recounted its experiences with the containerisation of the Icosahedral Non-hydrostatic (ICON) model running at scale. In the latter stages of the ESiWACE2 project, teams from Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), ETH Zurich (ETHZ), MeteoSwiss and the University of Reading implemented a container infrastructure within the production workflows. This milestone summarises these containerisation efforts, which will subsequently be presented in more detail in Deliverable D2.9 *Report summarising porting the different models to containers, including evaluation of the performance on the supercomputer where the containers are deployed*.

Three production models were foreseen for this milestone. However, these teams containerised four: EC-Earth (BSC), COSMO (ETH Zurich and MeteoSwiss), ICON (ETH Zurich) and LFRic (UReading). The status of each of these is given in the subsequent sections.

EC-Earth

The BSC team made very quick progress during the Container Hackathon (December 3-5, 2019, extensively reported in D2.8), containerising versions of two simplified EC-Earth configurations: One for the current stable version EC-Earth3, and another for the next generation EC-Earth4, which is currently under development. BSC considers the results of the hackathon as sufficiently successful to also satisfy the M48 reporting requirement.

COSMO

COSMO was in production at the German Weather Service (DWD) until 2015 and is still used for weather forecasting at MeteoSwiss, although it will be supplanted by ICON in 2023. Although it was not represented at the Container Hackathon (Dec. 2019), the fact that users now require outdated configurations to run since COSMO is no longer officially supported makes it an ideal candidate for containers, which can offer long-term stability for a given software stack.

The Center for Climate System Modeling (C2SM) at ETH Zurich took up the task of containerising COSMO in 2021. The resulting container workflow is documented in <https://github.com/C2SM/container> (public access) and contains the requisite Dockerfiles. The resulting COSMO-container is embedded in the Jenkins Continuous Integration (CI) system used by C2SM, where it runs in addition to the COSMO code built natively (without containers). Although runtimes vary due to the load characteristics of the Piz Daint platform at CSCS, the overhead for the containerisation is estimated to have less than 10% degradation in performance (see the runtime comparison on the title page).

ICON

The Icosahedral Non-hydrostatic model is essentially the successor of COSMO for numerical weather forecasting but can also be used for climate simulations. A prototype container for ICON was already the subject of Milestone M2.4 (MS4, Dec. 2020). While that prototype was largely successful, it was still a one-off: the ICON software and build system quickly moved on, and the Dockerfiles were no

¹ <https://github.com/eth-cscs/ContainerHackathon>

² <https://zenodo.org/record/4323261>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4322594>

longer maintained. The maintainability question for containers is a central consideration and needs to be addressed to make containers useful in the long term.

The success of inserting the COSMO into the production workflow (mentioned above) led C2SM to propose a similar approach for ICON. This workflow requires that ICON is built using the Spack⁴ package manager to manage ICON's many dependencies. Spack vastly simplifies the current ICON build system (which also includes the construction of the software stack), and thus would increase maintainability. Although this Spack-based build system is not yet in the official ICON release, the discussion about its inclusion is ongoing. The resulting Dockerfile becomes essentially a call to spack install.

The same container website⁵ contains the underlying Dockerfiles as well as documentation about the ICON containerisation. Latest benchmarks on CSCS Piz Daint indicate that container overhead is minimal when the SARUS⁶ container engine is used.

LFRic

LFRic is the new weather and climate modelling system being developed by the UK Met Office to replace the existing Unified Model (UM) in preparation for exascale computing in the 2020s. The LFRic Singularity container⁷ is being actively used for a number of projects. These include:

- Development of LFRic code on individuals' laptops.
- On ARCHER2⁸, the UK's academic supercomputer, using the Cray interconnect:
 - A C1152 (8.5 km) resolution on 81 nodes and 324 nodes and a C2304 (4.3 km) resolution on 324 nodes. This is the highest resolution we have ever run LFRic (Gungho, dynamics only). Limited from running further by Archer2 config.
 - It was used as part of the XIOS benchmarking study for the Excalidata project⁹.
 - It will form the basis of any future LFRic installations on ARCHER2.
- On Microsoft's Azure: It has been run (so far) on 5 nodes in Azure with much larger runs planned.
- On Jasmin¹⁰: As part of a proposed student's benchmarking project using OpenMP and the fast ethernet interconnect.
- On Dirac CSD3 system at Cambridge¹¹: Preparation for the I/O using both network fabric and advanced burst buffers as part of the Excalidata project, using the Infiniband interconnect.

Conclusions

Containers have proved to be an extremely useful tool when the long-term operation of software is required, beyond the longevity of the software stack, which is frequently updated on HPC platforms. As part of the ESIWACE2 project, containers have been successfully incorporated into the production workflows of at least three current Earth System models.

Additional information will be provided in the subsequent deliverable D2.9: *Report summarising porting the different models to containers, including evaluation of the performance on the supercomputer where the containers are deployed.*

⁴ <https://spack.io/>

⁵ <https://github.com/C2SM/container> (currently branch exclaim)

⁶ Sarus - An OCI-compatible container engine for HPC: <https://sarus.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

⁷ https://github.com/NCAS-CMS/LFRic_container

⁸ <https://www.archer2.ac.uk/>

⁹ <https://excalibur.ac.uk/projects/excalidata/>

¹⁰ <https://jasmin.ac.uk/>

¹¹ <https://www.hpc.cam.ac.uk/dirac-csd3>